

Development of superhydrophobic magnetic nanocellulose sponge for oil/water separation

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ABSTRACT

Tackling of severe environmental issues emerging from oil spill accidents and industrial oily waste water is a challenging task (1). Recently, sponge like 3D materials with superhydrophobic and superoleophilic properties have attracted considerable interest in the field of oil water separation owing to their excellent sorption capacity and high selectivity of oil (2-4). Herein, we have successfully fabricated Superhydrophobic and superoleophilic cellulose sponge from paper waste via freeze drying followed by silanization and achieved water contact angle $>150^\circ$ and oil contact angle nearly 0° . Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles were integrated on the surface of the cellulose sponge which facilitated collection of the sponge after oil separation. Morphological analysis was performed using Scanning Electron Microscopy. Oil absorption capacities, magnetic and mechanical properties of the sponge have been evaluated. The superhydrophobic magnetic nanocellulose sponge could separate oil/water mixture with high separation efficiency and good reusability.

Keywords: Superhydrophobicity, cellulose sponge, silanization, oil/water separation

References

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